

Lanthanide(III) f-f Transition Probabilities†

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The dynamic coupling mechanism for f-f transition probabilities in lanthanide(III) complexes is extended to include the polarisability-anisotropy of the ligands, with applications to complexes with D_{3h} and D_{5h} coordination polyhedra. The ligand-polarisation and the crystal-field mechanisms for f-f transition probabilities are found to be complementary, applying primarily to the lower and the higher even 2 λ -pole transitions, respectively.

THE f-f transitions of lanthanide and actinide coordination compounds belong to the general class, $\Delta l=0$, which includes the d-d excitation of transition metal complexes and the p-p promotions of heteroatoms in organic chromophores. The probabilities of $\Delta l=0$ transitions are sensitive to the particular stereochemistry and to the polarisability of the ligand groups in the molecular environment of the chromophore, whether an open-shell metal ion or an organic heteroatom. Over a series of compounds containing a common chromophore, the oscillator strength of a given $\Delta l=0$ transition is found to cover a range of more than two orders of magnitude, dependent upon the symmetry of the ligand array and the electronic softness of the ligand groups. The intensity range is common to the organic p-p type¹, the d-d class in transition metal complexes², and to the quadrupolar f-f transitions of lanthanide coordination compounds^{3,4}. For chiral stereochemistries, the rotational strengths of the $\Delta l=0$ transitions are even more sensitive to the particular location and to the polarisability of the ligand groups in the molecular environment of the chromophore⁵.

Localised-system mechanisms :

The localised-system model for electronic transition probabilities, where electron exchange between the chromophore and the ligands is neglected, was developed in two directions during the 1930s, in connection with the theory of optical activity. The one-electron theory⁶ postulated the mixing of the $\Delta l=0$ with $\Delta l=\pm 1$ electronic transitions of the chromophore under a static dissymmetric field due to the ligand groups. In contrast, the dynamic coupling theory⁷ proposed that the leading electric multipole moment of the chromophore transition induces, and couples to, a secondary electric transition dipole in each ligand group.

Both of the localised-systems mechanisms were applied to the p-p type excitations of organic chromophores, notably the $n\rightarrow\pi^*$ carbonyl transition of chiral ketones. Following the early studies^{8,9} the static coupling model was developed^{10,11} on the basis that, at the oxygen atom, the

$2p_y\rightarrow 2p_x$ component of the carbonyl $n\rightarrow\pi^*$ transition near 300 nm mixes with the corresponding Rydberg excitation, $2p_y\rightarrow 3d_{yz}$, under the Coulombic field of the incompletely-screened nuclei of the substituent atoms. In the corresponding development of the dynamic coupling model, it was proposed¹² that the leading electric moment of the carbonyl $n\rightarrow\pi^*$ transition, the xy-component of a quadrupole at the oxygen atom, induces a secondary electric dipole transition moment in a substituent group, dependent upon the polarisability of the group and its location in the molecular frame of the carbonyl chromophore. The electric dipole induced in the substituent group and the zero-order magnetic dipole moment have a scalar product which gives the carbonyl $n\rightarrow\pi^*$ transition a rotational strength conforming to the empirical octant rule¹³, while the corresponding dipole strength becomes enhanced¹³.

The parallel development of the localised-systems model for the f-f and the d-d transition probabilities in the lanthanide and transition metal coordination compounds was confined largely to the static-coupling mechanism, due to the general success of the crystal-field interpretation of the observed Stark-splittings of the corresponding transition energies. Following the pioneer applications¹⁴⁻¹⁶, the static coupling mechanism for the Laporte-forbidden¹⁷ transition probabilities was placed upon a quantitative basis for both the transition metal^{18,19} and the lanthanide^{20,21} coordination compounds.

The oscillator strengths of the d-d excitations in octahedral transition metal complexes are accommodated by the vibronic form of the static coupling mechanism¹³, whereas the values calculated for the corresponding electronic transitions in analogous tetrahedral complexes are too small by some two orders of magnitude¹⁹. A further anomaly became apparent from studies of the temperature dependence of the d-d absorption intensities. The d-d oscillator strengths of octahedral transition metal complexes are found to increase as the temperature is raised in accord with the vibronic static coupling mechanism. The intensity enhancement is due to the larger excursions from O_h symmetry with increasing tem-

† Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

perature, owing to the increasing population of the higher vibrational levels of the non-totally symmetric modes in the electronic ground state of the complex²². A similar trend is expected for tetrahedral complexes, but the contrary behaviour is observed²³.

Stereochemical ligand hypersensitivity :

In the parallel application of the static coupling mechanism and its vibronic extension to the f-f transition probabilities of lanthanide coordination compounds^{20,21}, an exceptional set of hypersensitive f-f excitations was identified, following the selection rules for electric quadrupole transitions⁹. The oscillator strength of a hypersensitive f-f excitation, such as the ${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4G_{5/2}$ transition of a Nd^{III} complex near 590 nm, covers a range of some three magnitude orders, dependent upon the stereochemical symmetry of the ligand set, the polarisability of the ligands, and the metal-ligand bond lengths⁴. At the lower end of the range, exemplified by Nd^{III} as a guest ion in the LaF₃ host lattice, static coupling estimates give the 590 nm transition an intensity compatible with experiment²⁴, but the corresponding estimates for other Nd^{III} complexes are too small, particularly for the trihalides NdX₃ in the vapour phase at the higher end of the range²⁵.

In the initial survey of the possible sources of f-f hypersensitivity, an inhomogeneous dielectric mechanism was suggested, based upon the quasi-diatomic model of a lanthanide ion coordinated to a ligand with a polarisability larger than that of the surrounding medium⁶. The ligand increases the spatial gradient of the electric field vector of the radiation across the lanthanide ion, and so enhances the f-f electric quadrupole transition probability⁸. Although intensity data were available for a number of lanthanide coordination compounds, the inhomogeneous dielectric mechanism was applied to no specific cases, and its potential as a dynamic coupling alternative to the standard static crystal field mechanism was not fully appreciated until recently^{26,27}.

Isotropic ligand polarisation :

The productive applications of the complementary dynamic coupling mechanism for the estimation of dipole and rotational strengths to the p-p excitations of chiral ketones^{12,13} prompted an extension of the mechanism to d-d and f-f transition probabilities in open-shell metal ion coordination compounds. The extension provided a quantitative analysis for the d-d rotational strengths²⁸ of the chiral tris-diamine complexes of cobalt(III), and for the relatively large d-d dipole strengths²⁹ and the singular negative temperature coefficient of those strengths³⁰ in the tetrahedral halide-ion complexes of cobalt(II). In addition, the d-d Faraday transition probabilities determined from the magnetically-induced circular dichroism spectra of tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes, while anomalous in sign according to static-coupling crystal field theory³¹⁻³³, are accommodated by the dynamic-coupling mechanism^{34,35}. Applied initially to investigate

the large oscillator strengths of the ${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^4G_{5/2}$ f-f transition of neodymium(III) in the gaseous trihalides³⁶, the dynamic ligand polarisation mechanism is found to account for a wide range of hypersensitive f-f intensities^{37,38}, including the dipole strengths vibronically-induced in centrosymmetric lanthanide coordination compounds³⁹.

The Laporte-forbidden $\Delta l=0$ electronic promotions, according to the ligand-polarisation model, acquire a first order electric dipole probability from the correlated resultant of electric dipoles induced in the individual ligands by an allowed even-multipole electric moment of the metal ion excitation. The allowed electric 2^λ -pole moments of a $\Delta l=0$ transition lie in the range, $2 < \lambda < 2l$, that is, a quadrupole only for p-p promotions, the 2^3 - and the 2^4 -pole for d-d excitations, and the 2^6 -pole additionally in the case of f-f transitions. Owing to the dependence of the potential between an electric 2^λ -pole and a dipole on $R_z^{-\lambda-2}$, where R_z is the metal-ligand bond length, the dynamic polarisation mechanism is the most effective for transitions with an electric quadrupole as the leading moment.

For isotropic ligands, such as the halide ions, or with ligands taken to have the mean polarisability $\bar{\alpha}_L(\nu_{om})$ at the metal ion transition frequency, the first order electric dipole moment, μ_{om}^{ν} , of the metal ion excitation, $M_o \rightarrow M_m$, with the electric quadrupole component, $\theta_{om}^{\alpha\beta}$, as its leading moment is given by the relation,

$$\mu_{om}^{\nu} = - \sum_L \theta_{om}^{\alpha\beta} G_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^L \bar{\alpha}_L(\nu_{om}) \quad (1)$$

where, the sum is taken over the ligands, L. The geometric tensor $G_{\alpha\beta\gamma}^L$ represents the radial and angular terms governing the potential between the electric quadrupole component, $\theta_{om}^{\alpha\beta}$, centred on the metal ion, and the induced dipole, with γ -polarisation, located in the ligand, L. The Greek suffixes (α, β, γ) denote cartesian components (x, y or z) in the coordinate frame of the metal complex.

The development of equation (1) for a given $|f^N J\rangle \rightarrow |f^N J'\rangle$ quadrupolar transition of the metal ion in a complex with a single set of symmetry-related ligands affords an expression for the dipole strength of the transition as a function of the L-M-L bond angle, with a constant M-L bond length^{26,35}. Relative to a unit dipole strength for the corresponding monocoordinate diatomic M-L case, a trigonal ML₃ complex has a ligand polarisation dipole strength which varies with the cosine of the L-M-L bond angle, c , according to the function, $3[1-3c+5c^2]$, over the stereochemical range from D_{3h} to C_{3v}. For trigonal complexes ML₃, notably, the lanthanide trihalides in the vapour phase, the dipole strength is an optimum for the bond angle of 117°, but the ligand polarisation intensity is only 1% smaller at the D_{3h} equilibrium nuclear configuration. The corresponding expression for the regular four-coordinate complexes over the general D_{2d} range, $\{-60[c+c^2+c^3]\}$, shows that the ligand polarisation dipole strength is optimum

for an exact tetrahedral stereochemistry. The singular temperature-decrease in the dipole strengths of the quadrupole-allowed d-d transitions of the cobalt(II) tetrahalides is due to the large vibrational excursions from regular T_d symmetry with an increase in temperature^{30,35}.

Anisotropic ligand polarisation :

New features of the dynamic polarisation mechanism emerged from the analyses of the single crystal polarised spectra of the trigonal europium(III) complexes, $[\text{Eu}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_9](\text{EtSO}_4)_3$ (I), $\text{Na}_3[\text{Eu}(\text{ODA})_3] \cdot \text{NaClO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (II), and $\text{Gd}(\text{Eu})\text{Al}_3(\text{BO}_3)_4$ (III). The $[\text{EuO}_9]$ cluster in each of the complexes (I) and (II) is made up of two ligand sets, a trigonal planar $[\text{ML}_3]$ group and a superimposed trigonal prism $[\text{ML}_6]$ group, the latter being regular (D_{3h}) in the nonhydrate (I), but distorted (D_3) in the complex (II), where each tridentate ODA ligand consists of the dianion of oxy-diacetic acid $[\text{O}(\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2)_2]^{2-}$. The two D_{3h} ligand sets in the nonhydrate (I) are displaced by a small angle, ca. 5° , from the staggered configuration, so that the $[\text{EuO}_9]$ chromophore has C_{3h} symmetry overall. The six-coordinate $[\text{EuO}_6]$ cluster of the borate (III) has the D_3 distorted trigonal prism symmetry⁴⁰.

trigonal prism ligand set, the complex (III) has a $\Delta M_J = \pm 2$ dipole strength larger by an order of magnitude than the corresponding strength of either the complex (I) or (II) (Table 1). In contrast, the pure magnetic-dipole transition ${}^7F_0 \rightarrow {}^5D_1$, is ligand-insensitive, and has a similar dipole strength in each of the Eu^{III} complexes⁴⁰ (Fig. 1, Table 1).

Fig. 1. The electric dipole moments induced in the ligands of a 9-coordinate trigonal Ln^{III} complex by the $(x^2 - y^2)$ component of the electric quadrupole f-f transition moment of the metal ion, showing the negative interference between the resultant induced dipole of the equatorial $[\text{ML}_3]$ ligand set and that of the $[\text{ML}_6]$ trigonal prism ligand set.

The application of equation (1) to the $\Delta M_J = \pm 2$ component of the ${}^7F_0 \rightarrow {}^5D_3$ f-f transition of Eu^{III} at a trigonal site, where the (xy) and $(x^2 - y^2)$ components of an electric quadrupole are the leading transition moments, shows that the contribution of both the $[\text{ML}_3]$ and the $[\text{ML}_6]$ ligand set to the first order electric dipole transition moment is substantial. The two contributions are out of phase, however, so that the net resultant is small in the complexes (I) and (II). With only the $[\text{ML}_6]$

The treatment of the $\Delta M_J = \pm 1$ component of the ${}^7F_0 \rightarrow {}^5D_3$ f-f transition of Eu^{III} , with the (yz) and (zx) components of an electric quadrupole as the leading moments at a trigonal site, requires a consideration of the anisotropy of the ligand polarisability. The $\Delta M_J = \pm 1$ component is observed in the spectra of the D_3 complexes (II) and (III), but not in that of the C_{3h} nonhydrate (I), as expected on group-theoretical grounds. The mean polarisability approximation of the dynamic coupling mechanism (equation 1) fails to account for the observed $\Delta M_J = \pm 1$ dipole strengths. These are accommodated by the inclusion of the ligand anisotropy through the relation,

$$\langle 0 | \mu_y^{(1)} | m \rangle = - \langle 0 | \theta_{yz}^{(2)} | m \rangle \sum_{\alpha} [\alpha_{yz} G_{\alpha}^{(2)}]_{L^{(1)}} \quad (2)$$

where, $\alpha_{yz}^{(2)}$ refers to the $\nu\delta$ -component of the polarisability tensor of the ligand L in the global coordinate frame of the complex at the transition frequency. The electric dipole polarisability tensor of a ligand is made up of the three irreducible sets, $\alpha^{(0)}$, $\alpha^{(1)}$, and $\alpha^{(2)}$. The scalar mean polarisability, $\alpha^{(0)}$, enters into equation (1), whereas the five symmetric polarisability components, forming an irreducible second rank tensor, $\alpha^{(2)}$, are of primary concern in equation (2).

Recent theoretical analysis of the dynamic coupling mechanism^{41,42}, and an earlier study of crystal field and general one-electron mechanisms for f-f transition probabilities⁴³, show that the

TABLE 1—EUROPIUM(III) COORDINATION COMPLEXES

Frequency $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm⁻¹) and dipole strength D_{0m} (10⁻⁶ e²cm²) of the zero-order magnetic dipole ${}^7F_0 \rightarrow {}^5D_1$ and electric quadrupole ${}^7F_0 \rightarrow {}^5D_2$ f-f transition of Eu^{III} observed in the axial (ax) and in the polarised (π parallel, σ perpendicular) *ortho*-axial single crystal spectra of (I) [Eu(H₂O)₉](EtSO₄)₃, (II) Na₃[Eu(ODA)₃].4NaClO₄.6H₂O, (III) Gd(Eu)Al₃(BO₃)₄, and the spectrum of (IV) [Eu(bpyO₂)₄](ClO₄) in acetonitrile solution

Transition component (polarisation)	I (C _{3h})		II (D ₃)		III (D ₃)		IV (D ₄)	
	$\tilde{\nu}$	D_{0m}	$\tilde{\nu}$	D_{0m}	$\tilde{\nu}$	D_{0m}	$\tilde{\nu}$	D_{0m}
${}^7F_0 \rightarrow {}^5D_1$ $\Delta M = \pm 1$ (π + ax)	19 020	30	18 981	31	18 966	38	18 990	23
$\Delta M = 0$ (σ)	19 024	26	18 965	24	18 995	23		
${}^7F_0 \rightarrow {}^5D_2$ $\Delta M = \pm 2$ (σ + ax)	21 499	10	21 433	14	21 419	230	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>
$\Delta M = \pm 1$ (σ + ax)	<i>a</i>	<i>a</i>	21 484	62	21 491	220	21 470	680

a = Absent.

introduction of the polarisability anisotropy of the ligands increases the scope of the dynamic mechanism by widening the range of the allowed ranks (*t*) of the ligand-dependent tensor, $[\alpha_{\gamma\delta} G_{\alpha\beta\delta}^{(t)}]_L^{(t)}$ in equation (2). If the polarisability of the ligand group is contracted to the scalar mean value, the tensor overall is limited to rank-3, the rank of the geometric component, $G_{\alpha\beta\delta}^{(3)}$. The rank restriction is not necessarily lifted on taking the polarisability anisotropy of the ligands into account, notably, for the higher coordination symmetries, such as C_{3h}, D_{3h} or T_d, where the point group operations limit the coordinated ligand groups to an effectively cylindrical form around a metal-ligand bond axis.

More generally, the representation of the ligand polarisability element, $\alpha_{\gamma\delta}^L$, by one of the five components of the symmetric second rank polarisability tensor of the ligand group requires, in equation (2), an introduction of the direction cosines referring to the orientation of the ligand bonds considered in the overall frame of the coordination polyhedron¹². Thereby, the element, $\alpha_{\gamma\delta}^L$, is transformed into the local diagonal form in terms of the anisotropy invariant, $\beta_x = (\alpha_{11} - \alpha_{\perp})_L$, on the assumption of an effectively cylindrical ligand bond symmetry. Each set of direction cosines forms a tensor of rank-2 and contraction extends the range of allowed ranks (*t*) of the ligand dependent tensor, $[\alpha_{\gamma\delta} G_{\alpha\beta\delta}^{(t)}]_L^{(t)}$ in equation (2), to first and second, in addition to the third-rank tensor alone required in the corresponding scalar mean-polarisability approximation (equation 1).

The even, second-rank, ligand-dependent tensors are unique to the anisotropic ligand polarisation mechanism for quadrupolar $\Delta l = 0$ electronic transitions. The corresponding ligand-dependent terms of the crystal field mechanism, A_{β}^t , are necessarily odd, with *t* = 1, 3 for quadrupolar electronic promotions, and they imply cylindrically symmetric metal-ligand interaction. Local C_{∞v} symmetry around each metal-ligand bond is precluded in coordination polyhedra with dihedral symmetry and, for the quadrupolar metal ion excita-

tions, only the rank-2 ligand dependent tensors survive in a D₄ coordination cluster^{41,42}. The rank-2 tensor mediates solely the $\Delta M_J = \pm 1$ quadrupolar transition component in a D₄ complex, as in the D₃ cases of [Eu(ODA)₃]³⁻ and Gd(Eu)Al₃(BO₃)₄ where, additionally, a rank-3 ligand-dependent tensor governs both the anisotropic and the mean isotropic polarisability contributions of the ligand groups to the probability of the corresponding $\Delta M_J = \pm 2$ transition component^{40,44} (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Only a second rank field polarisation tensor, dependent on the ligand polarisability anisotropy, survives for electric quadrupole transitions of D₄ complexes, restricted to the yz- and the degenerate zx- component of the quadrupole transition moment.

The eight-coordinate tetrakis(2,2'-bipyridine-*N,N'*-dioxide)lanthanum perchlorate crystal structure⁴⁵ indicates that the complex cation has D₄ symmetry, and the spectrum of the analogue, [Eu(bpyO₂)₄](ClO₄)₃ (IV), in the region of the ${}^7F_0 \rightarrow {}^5D_2$ absorption shows only the $\Delta M_J = \pm 1$ component, assigned from a comparison of its frequency with that of the corresponding component for the D₃ analogues (II) and (III) (Table 1). The dipole

strength of the component for the complex (IV) is consistent, through equation (2), with the measured polarisability anisotropies of the ligand bonds, including that of the N-oxide bond⁴⁶, which makes the major intensity contribution⁴⁴. While the $\Delta M_J = \pm 1$ component of the ${}^7F_0 \rightarrow {}^5D_3$ transition in the D_3 analogues (II) and (III) has an electric dipole probability governed similarly by a unique rank-2 polarisation tensor, the upper state has E symmetry in D_3 , like the upper state of the corresponding $\Delta M_J = \pm 2$ component, and M_J -mixing cannot be ruled out in the D_3 cases. A corresponding M_J -mixing is not feasible in the complex (IV), since states with B_1 and B_2 symmetry result from the $\Delta M_J = \pm 2$ component and only the upper state of the $\Delta M_J = \pm 1$ component has E symmetry in the D_4 group of (IV). Thus both the crystal field and the isotropic ligand polarisation intensity mechanism are ruled out for the D_4 complex (IV), leaving anisotropic ligand polarisation as the sole localised-systems mechanism consistent with the observed dipole strength⁴⁴.

Complementary static and dynamic coupling intensity contribution :

The theory of f-f transition probabilities due to Judd²⁰ and Ofelt²¹ provides, for a given lanthanide coordination compound, a set of three dipole strength parameters, Ω_λ ($\lambda=2, 4$ or 6), which may be compared with the corresponding observed quantities. Although the Judd-Ofelt theory was formulated on the electrostatic crystal field basis^{20,21}, the intensity parameterisation is general for all one-electron mechanisms⁴⁸. The empirical intensity parameters are obtained from the manifold of $J \rightarrow J'$ bands, each with the dipole strength $D_{JJ'}$, observed in the f-f spectrum of the Ln^{III} complex through the relation,

$$D_{JJ'} = (2J+1)^{-1} \sum_{\lambda} \Omega_{\lambda} | \langle J' \| U^{(\lambda)} \| J \rangle |^2 \quad (3)$$

The reduced matrix elements in equation (3), $\langle J' \| U^{(\lambda)} \| J \rangle$, refer to the unit tensor $U^{(\lambda)}$ operating within the $4f^N$ configuration and express the fractional even 2^λ -pole moment of the $J \rightarrow J'$ transition. The corresponding dipole strength parameters, Ω_λ , represent the square modulus of the first order electric dipole moment of the f-f excitation, whether of a crystal field or another origin, associated with the zero-order electric 2^λ -pole moment ($\lambda=2, 4$ or 6) of the transition. With a set of the reduced matrix elements of $U^{(\lambda)}$, a least-squares analysis of the manifold of $J \rightarrow J'$ intensities in the spectrum of a given Ln^{III} complex provides the three empirical $\Omega_\lambda(\text{obs})$ parameters^{47,48}.

The crystal field and the ligand polarisation mechanisms for f-f transition probabilities are independent within the localised-systems model, and the first order electric dipole moments given by the two mechanisms for a particular excitation are vectorially additive. The expression for the total dipole strength parameter, $\Omega_\lambda(\text{tot})$, of the $J \rightarrow J'$ manifold exhibited by a particular Ln^{III} complex

contains terms corresponding, not only to the square modulus of each first order electric dipole moment, $\Omega_\lambda(\text{CF})$ for the crystal field contribution and $\Omega_\lambda(\text{LP})$ for the ligand polarisation contribution, but also to a pseudoscalar cross term, $\Omega_\lambda(\text{CT})$, between the static and the dynamic component of the first order electric-dipole transition moment,

$$\Omega_\lambda(\text{tot}) = \Omega_\lambda(\text{CF}) + \Omega_\lambda(\text{LP}) + \Omega_\lambda(\text{CT}) \quad (4)$$

The cross term, $\Omega_\lambda(\text{CT})$, is non-vanishing for a first order static field and dynamic coupling electric dipole moment with the same polarisation, connected with a common component of a given zero-order electric 2^λ -pole moment of the metal ion transition⁴⁹⁻⁵¹.

The ligand polarisation dipole strength parameter, $\Omega_\lambda(\text{LP})$, represents essentially the square modulus of the first order electric-dipole transition moment of equations (1) and (2) and the analogous expressions for the corresponding zero-order electric 2^λ - and 2^0 -pole moments of the metal ion transition. The crystal field dipole strength parameter, $\Omega_\lambda(\text{CF})$, is made up of two principal terms, one dependent solely on the metal ion, $P_{\lambda t}$, which expresses the mixing of a f-f transition possessing a leading 2^λ -pole moment with a dipolar $4f \rightarrow 5d$ or $4f \rightarrow ng$ transition, and the other dependent only on the ligands, $A_{\lambda t}^{\pm}$, representing the odd-parity electrostatic crystal field experienced by the metal ion,

$$\Omega_\lambda(\text{CF}) = (2\lambda+1) \sum_{t=1}^{\tau} \sum_{m=-t}^{+t} | P_{\lambda t} A_{\lambda t}^{\pm} |^2 (2t+1)^{-1} \quad (5)$$

The order (t) of the crystal field parameter $A_{\lambda t}^{\pm}$ is restricted to the values, $t=(\lambda \pm 1)$, with $\lambda=2, 4$ or 6 .

Estimates of the crystal field and the ligand polarisation contributions to the overall dipole strength of particular $J \rightarrow J'$ f-electron transitions in the complexes $[\text{Ln}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_9]^{3+}$ (I) and $[\text{Ln}(\text{ODA})_3]^{3-}$ (II), for the Ln^{III} cases of Pr, Eu, Tb and Ho, indicate that the crystal field contribution is generally dominant, the ligand polarisation contribution being of comparable significance only for the hypersensitive quadrupolar transitions^{49,50}. In complexes of the structural types (I) and (II), the ligand polarisation contribution to the first order electric-dipole transition moment is minimised by negative interference, due to the out-of-phase relation between the individual contributions of the $[\text{ML}_3]$ and the $[\text{ML}_6]$ ligand sets⁴⁰. Moreover, for D_3 and higher dihedral coordination polyhedra, such as the complex (II), only the anisotropic polarisability contributions (equation 2) are non-zero for $\Delta M_J = \pm 1$ transitions^{40,44}, and these contributions were not taken into account in the estimates^{49,50}.

The eight-coordinate tetrakis(dithiocarbamate)- Ln^{III} complexes, $\text{Na}[\text{Ln}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})_4]$, provide a more comprehensive comparison of the relative crystal field and ligand polarisation contributions to the overall dipole strength parameters, Ω_λ (equation 4), for the majority of the lanthanides⁵¹. Crystals of

the coordination compounds, $\text{Na}[\text{Ln}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})_4]$, are isomorphous over the lanthanide range La to Yb, and the crystal structure of the La^{III} complex shows that the $[\text{LaS}_6]$ cluster has the stereochemical form of a distorted dodecahedron, in which the four CS_2 chelate groups are arranged at the vertices of a quasi-tetrahedron^{5a}. The transition frequencies and the dipole strengths over the generally accessible f-f manifold have been determined for the majority of the $\text{Na}[\text{Ln}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})_4]$ complexes^{5a}, allowing an extraction of the three dipole strength parameters, Ω_λ with $\lambda=2, 4$ or 6 , for each member of the series.

The calculated estimates of the total dipole strength parameters, $\Omega_\lambda(\text{tot})$, for the series of $[\text{Ln}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})_4]^-$ complexes are in fair agreement with the corresponding empirical values $\Omega_\lambda(\text{obs})$ for $\lambda=4$ and 6 directly and for $\Omega_2(\text{tot})$ with an allowance for the screening of the 4f electrons by the outer $5s^2 5p^6$ shell^{5a}, partly compensated by nephelauxetic effects. In principle^{5a}, the Hartree-Fock radial expectation values for the 4f electrons of the Ln^{III} ion, $\langle r^\lambda \rangle_{\text{HF}}$, require scaling by a screening, σ_λ , and an antiscreening, τ_λ , factor to give the effective value, $\langle r^\lambda \rangle_{\text{eff}}$, where,

$$\langle r^\lambda \rangle_{\text{eff}} / \langle r^\lambda \rangle_{\text{HF}} = (1 - \sigma_\lambda) / \tau_\lambda \quad (6)$$

For the series of $[\text{Ln}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})_4]^-$ complexes, the comparison of the $\Omega_\lambda(\text{tot})$ estimates with the corresponding $\Omega_\lambda(\text{obs})$ values indicates^{5a} that the screening/antiscreening ratio (equation 6), while approximating to unity for $\lambda=4, 6$, has a value, in the case of $\lambda=2$, of ca. 0.8 for the heavier lanthanides and decreases over the lighter lanthanides to ca. 0.5 for Pr^{III} . Calculated values^{5a} of the screening constants σ_4 and σ_6 are small, but the values obtained for σ_2 are 0.675 for Tm^{III} and as large as 0.825 for Pr^{III} . These theoretical σ_2 values indicate that the antiscreening constant τ_2 approximates to 0.4, due largely to nephelauxetic and Ln^{2+} charge-reduction effects^{5a} (Fig. 3).

Overall the calculated dipole strength parameters (equation 4) show that the dynamic polarisation mechanism is important mainly for the hypersensitive quadrupolar f-f transitions, as originally envisaged^{5a, 5b} from the dependence of $\Omega_\lambda(\text{LP})$ upon $R_z^{-2\lambda-4}$. There are no major differences between the relative crystal-field and ligand-polarisation contributions to the $\Omega_\lambda(\text{tot})$ values across the series of $\text{Na}[\text{Ln}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})_4]$ complexes from Pr to Yb. On an average over the series, the ligand polarisation contribution to $\Omega_\lambda(\text{tot})$ decreases from 66 to 17 and to 0.1% for $\lambda=2, 4, 6$, respectively, while the corresponding crystal field contribution increases from 5 to 57 and 98.5%, respectively. The remaining pseudoscalar cross term component, $\Omega_\lambda(\text{CT})$ in equation (4), is significant for $\lambda=2$ and 4 , contributing the respective average of 29 and 25%, respectively^{5a, 5b}.

Conclusion :

Within the general independent-systems model, the static and the dynamic coupling mechanisms

Fig. 3. The relationship across the series of lanthanide coordination compounds, $\text{Na}[\text{Ln}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})_4]$, between the observed, $\Omega_\lambda(\text{obs})$, and the total calculated dipole strength parameter, $\Omega_\lambda(\text{tot})$ (equation 4), with a screening/antiscreening ratio (equation 6) of unity for $\lambda=4, 6$ and with the value of 0.8 for $\lambda=2$.

provide complementary first order perturbation treatments of $\Delta l=0$ electronic transition probabilities. The multiplet-to-multiplet f-f intensities of the excitations with an electric 2nd-pole as the leading moment are governed predominantly by the crystal field mechanism in the $[\text{Ln}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})_4]^-$ complexes, and probably in all lanthanide coordination compounds. The dynamic polarisation mechanism has its salient applications to the probabilities of $\Delta l=0$ transitions with an electric quadrupole or, to a lesser degree, an electric hexadecapole as the leading moment in noncentric compounds with a single set of polarisable ligands, which are symmetry-related, or approximately so. Where there are multiple sets of ligands with a small polarisability, as in the case of the Ln^{III} guest ions in the LaF_3 host lattice, both the crystal field^{5a} and the ligand polarisation^{5b} treatments account individually for the observed quadrupolar f-f intensities, and the two mechanisms are not distinguished.

A distinction between the two mechanisms may be drawn from the restriction of the ligand-dependent crystal field parameters, A_p^t (equation 5) to the odd values, $t=(\lambda \pm 1)$, with $\lambda=2, 4$ or 6 , depending upon the leading electric 2^λ -pole of the metal ion transition. A group-theoretical treatment of the electric dipole intensity parameters for f-f transitions shows that the range is restrictive, the even value, $t=\lambda$, being allowed additionally for more

general one-electron mechanisms⁴³. The corresponding dynamic coupling ligand-dependent parameters, including the components of the symmetric second-rank polarisability tensor of the ligands, [$\chi^{(2)}G^{(\lambda+1)}(t)$], have the range of ranks $t=\lambda, (\lambda\pm 1)$, required group-theoretically⁴⁰⁻⁴⁴. The even-rank value, $t=\lambda$, is particular to the dynamic coupling mechanism and, for quadrupolar $\Delta l=0$ transitions in coordination compounds with D_4 and higher dihedral symmetry, such as (IV), the only non-zero dynamic polarisation intensity parameters are second rank, like those of the $\Delta M_r = \pm 1$ quadrupolar transitions in the D_2 complexes (II) and (III).

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